

Mobile Robot 3D Localization based in Object Incenter detection

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Abstract: Nowadays the processing techniques for localization in unknown areas are based on feature extraction algorithms from determined geometric figures, and from that features obtaining information and compare with between scans. This paper tackles a new technique for improving the processing time in 3D mapping and localization problem, based on a determined feature, the propose extends to a full object detection, in this case sphere object and measure the localization based on the displacement of the sphere center.

Keywords: Mobile robot, point cloud, computer vision, path planning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Localization in 3D environment always represents a challenge for the autonomous mobile robot scene, and about it several efforts were displays trying to find an efficient solution for localization on 3D scenarios, however is important to consider maps as highly complex algorithm so just finding the localization is no enough in order to obtain a full response about all the surrounding environment.

First is important to highlight the maps created by the laser range finders, but is clear that those are not using any semantic information [1], there are a couple more were approaches making localization using stereo cameras for representations of 3D models [2], we could mention a previous work based on an object based approach but in this case are using cognitive maps as difference with the laser range finders maps [3], are several approaches identifying how construct maps from raw data as it show on [4], from it as well we could construct planar features extracted from the point cloud show in [5], were mostly all those works are based on the plane extraction, but it could be tackle faster obtaining data directly from specific geometric features instead of processing the full point cloud and extract the planar info.

Making the robot explore in a large environment over a long period of time always represent a challenge, currently this task is well develop on the 2D scene for mobile robotics, and exist robust algorithm for mapping and localization, for the 2D case is mostly based on feature extraction from the information generated for any sensor and is mostly used for those applications the laser range finder, nowadays for the 3D scenario require handle big amount of information and for it we recreate a point cloud using the same laser range finder, the most of the techniques are pretty much following the same concept as in 2D, which is obtain a feature and then compare using the ICP algorithm [6] to match the feature and find out the displacement, but it takes a important amount of time and the algorithm efficiency

is relative high, the current paper propose the same concept but extending the algorithm in extracting the full geometric figure and not just a feature, with it the goal is obtaining a robust response, reducing the processing time and improving the accuracy for better robot localization.

2. POINT CLOUD GENERATION

To tackle the problem of 3D localization is necessary understand how to transform all the information collected buy the laser range finder in 2D, the way that we generate the 3D information is combining the 2D laser sensor with a crack mechanism, this concept was mention in [7], where the idea is describe by the obtaining the info from a motor encoder angle θ relative to a link in a fix position where the 2D range data (P_{Lx}, P_{Ly}) and the obtained rotation at different heights meanwhile the robot is stationary resulting ($P_{Gx} = P_{Lx}, P_{Gy}, P_{Gz}$) Thought the following matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P_{Gx} \\ P_{Gy} \\ P_{Gz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\theta^*) & 0 \\ 0 & \sin(\theta^*) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P_{Lx} \\ P_{Ly} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

Basically the rotation matrix is used with two purposes, the first is to obtain the transformation matrix from the rotation mechanism, and second is to obtain the robot localization, given a interpolation between the first and the last scan results as:

$$T_t^{t+i}(x_i, y_i, \theta_i) = T_G \frac{i}{n}, i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (2)$$

And finally combining rotation system and the moving of the robot:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P_{GX}^{t+i} \\ P_{GY}^{t+i} \\ P_{GZ}^{t+i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_i) & -\sin(\theta_i) & x_i \\ \sin(\theta_i) & \cos(\theta_i) & y_i \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P_{LX} \\ P_{LY} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\theta^*) & 0 \\ 0 & \sin(\theta^*) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P_{LX}^{t+1} \\ P_{LY}^{t+1} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

3. SPHERE OBJECT EXTRACTION FROM POINT CLOUD

Once is obtain the point cloud according with the method describe above, we proceed to detect the range of interest of the points which resemble to sphere shape and setting up the diameter of the sphere, we could obtain the indices and extract the geometry model based in the equation:

$$(x - a)^2 + (y - b)^2 + (z - c)^2 = d^2, \quad (5)$$

As simple as based in this model we could construct the sphere, and localize the center point and use as reference for detecting the robot displacement.

Fig. 1 Description of the point cloud use for the Sphere Extraction.

4. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

The Experiment were performed using a Kuboki robot and a Hokuyo URG-04LX 2D laser rangefinder scanner in one of the university hall, the data were acquired on two different positions, for position A and B the point cloud was obtained under the same angle resolution.

Center Point localize, use a reference for distance measurement.

Fig. 2Description of the point cloud use for the Sphere Object Extraction.

As the results showed in the Figure 2, we could determine the sphere center point that for the robot position A and B as it corresponds:

Table 1 Robot position, and correspondents sphere object coordinates.

	x	y	z
A	$2.32 * 10^3$	$3.089 * 10^2$	$2.24 * 10^2$
B	$1.41 * 10^3$	$3.13 * 10^2$	94.053

And then just measuring the Euclidean distance between two 3D points:

$$\text{Displacement}=924.561$$

Using this value, we could measure the how long the robot have moved just by considering a single object as reference.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The results are based on the sphere object detection, even though the geometry for sphere is simple comparing with other figures, the idea is extend the concept to localize more geometrical shapes as cube, pyramid, cylinder and recreate the 3D map based in this kind of figures, and try to simplify the process submit previously in [8], in parallel to this goal is using the concept of incenter localization and extend it 3D mapping and path planning on mobile ground and aerial robots.

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